

Real Time Smart Car Parking System Using Internet of Things

Fikri Hanif

Center for Computing and Information
Technology, Faculty of Engineering,
Universitas Indonesia, Depok 16424,
Indonesia
e-mail: fikrihanif2407@gmail.com

Faculty: Mr. Mhd Idham Khalif, S.Kom
Center for Computing and Information
Technology, Faculty of Engineering,
Universitas Indonesia, Depok 16424,
Indonesia
e-mail: mhd.idham@ui.ac.i

Abstract— This position paper goes for smart car parking framework dependent on IOT. Because of expanding population and the quantity of vehicles, individuals are confronting issues on parking vehicles in a city. Along these lines, we thought of planning a framework called Smart Car Parking System which helps the drivers by giving data about accessibility of parking spaces in that particular zone. And furthermore, gives the alternative of advanced booking of parking space with the assistance of an Android application. Due to which consumption of fuel, time as well as pollution is reduced.

Keyword: *IoT, Internet of Things, MCU8266, IR sensors, parking slots, car parking, android application, pre-booking.*

I. INTRODUCTION

“A real-time system controls the environment by obtaining data, processing it, and giving out the results sufficiently, immediately to affect the environment at the same time.” [16]

“The Internet of things (IoT) is the use of Internet in physical devices and objects we interact with on a daily basis. Composed of internet connectivity, electronics, some hardware components, these devices can inter-communicate and interact with other components over the Internet. These different devices can be remotely monitored, analysed and controlled.” [16]

This position paper describes smart car parking system based on IOT. Vehicle parking is a noteworthy issue in present day which has clogged urban communities of today. There are basically an excessive number of vehicles out on the road and comparatively insufficient parking spaces. This has prompted the requirement for proficient smart parking frameworks which will provide ease and consume less time in searching for parking spaces. In this way, we exhibit the utilization of IoT based framework that takes into consideration productive parking spot use that saves space and time. To exhibit the idea, we use IR sensors for detecting the vehicles which arrives at the parking lot. We presently use MCU8266 microcontroller as the main unit for managing all the hardware functionality of our concept. This

microcontroller has an inbuilt Wi-Fi module for web connectivity and other services.

We use cloud-based server space for maintaining an online database and for handling the hardware signals coming to and from the MCU 8266 and the user application. The framework identifies if parking spaces are occupied or not with the help of IR sensors. Likewise, it utilizes IR innovation to detect if a vehicle has arrived at the parking space. The framework peruses the quantity of parking spaces accessible and refreshes information with the cloud server. This enables clients to check for accessible parking spots online from anyplace. Consequently, the framework reduces the time-consuming parking issue for urban areas and get clients a productive IoT based parking system framework.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The parking management problem can be viewed from several angles. Limited number of parking lots, drivers not knowing where parking lots are, drivers not sure if parking lots have enough space and a tendency to park illegally on the roads.

Due to above such issues, major problems faced by people are consumption of fuel, pollution, wastage of time, mental stress, etc.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Smart car parking system help us to reduce chaos of vehicles for parking place. Most of the time, in case of some places, there is no parking space available. So that, people park their vehicles on the road itself. This creates very bad picture and acts as a hurdle in everyone’s life. This project is useful for avoiding this situation.

Fig. 1 Proposed System to overcome problems occurring in current parking system

Fig.1 drawn above demonstrate four important part of smartcar parking system including hardware, cloud, admin website and a user application. As per the live data present at the cloud we provide its access to the user application. By using this data user get knowledge of number of available parking slots as well as occupied parking slots. The user can book slot according to his/her choice from available parking slot. As a result, the state of parking resources is changed by user's parking decisions. All this information is updated on admin website. The admin has an authority to accept or decline user's request. All this database is uploaded on cloud and admin handles it. The hardware is connected to the user application with the help of cloud.

Hardware used in this system i.e. IR sensors detects whether the car is present there or not and then it will pass this information towards MCU 8266. MCU will update this information on cloud. With the help of databases collected, admin can keep account of each user.

Due to this proposed system fuel as well as time for searching parking space will be reduced. It will be helpful for user and unorganized parking on the road will be reduced.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND WORKING

Before this section, we have discussed about the architecture and technical terminologies that are used in the smart parking. Here we are going to see how actually in real world this Smart Parking is going to work.

For this, we have designed a flow chart elaborating the flow of working of Real Time Smart Car Parking System using IoT.

A. Flow chart:

Fig. 2 Flow Chart of smart car parking system using IoT

B. Steps involved:

We have formed a real-world model representing the minimized view of the parking lot structure. We applied all the systems there and checked how actual system is going to perform.

Here are steps:

Step 1: Complete the installation of smart parking android application at user side.

Step 2: Do registration and login.

Step 3: Click on book slot. You will get status of all available and parked slots.

Step 4: Click on available slots to request for parking.

Step 5: Now request will be get updated to admin panel. When you reached the parking area admin will accept your request and allow you to enter.

Step 6: IR sensors are continuously detecting that if car is arrived or present or not.

Step 7: If car gets detected then it gets updated on application as well as website via cloud.

Step 8: Whenever you will leave the parking lot, the particular parking slot gets free and updated on each platform.

V. RESULT

To get proper understanding of the system it is mandatory to analyse all kinds of results we are receiving from the system. By all such analysis we are possible to reach our desired results. The previously mentioned procedure for booking a space is explained with the assistance of the following screen captures.

The figure 3 describes the registration and login page for the user application.

Fig.3 Registration page and login page of user application

In fig 4, here the green parking slots shows us that they are occupied, yellow parking slots are requested by user but didn't arrive at the location yet while red parking slots are totally available for the booking.

Fig.4 Parking slots

Fig.5 shows live status of parking slot at admin panel.

Fig.5 Admin Panel

Fig. 6 shows booking list of users at admin panel it also shows user's entry and exit time according to real time system.

Slot No	Book Time	Entry Time	Exit Time	Slot No	User Name	Vehicle No	Status
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked
1	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	2019-10-24 09:40	1	Yatish Bharambe	MH 1 CB 1111	Booked

Fig.6 Booking List for users

We design a hardware to achieve this work. In which we design a PCB to fulfil our needs of the hardware where we can put MCUNODE 8266 that is IoT Wi-Fi module, IR sensors and LEDs.

Fig7. Hardware of smart car parking system using IoT

In figure 7, we have designed hardware with Wi-Fi module, LEDs, IR sensors embedded on it. Which is working on 5 V DC.

Fig.8 Hardware with IRSensors and LEDs

VI. CONCLUSION

The idea of Smart Cities has dependably been a revolution for humankind. Since the recent years substantial breakthroughs have been made in making keen urban areas a reality. The development of Internet of Things and Cloudadvances have offered ascent to new potential outcomes as far as brilliant urban areas.

We have introduced a constant real time smart parking system utilizing IOT which disposes of the need to scan for parking spots and to productively choose and pre-book the ideal parking space. The user is thus feasible enough to get a parking slot as per its own choice at any time and from

anywhere using just the mobile application. The whole system works in real time as well as lots of problems like wastage of time, fuel consumption, pollution, etc. are minimized drastically.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Geng and C. G. Cassandras, "A new smart parking system based on optimal resource allocation and reservations in Proc. 14th Int. IEEE Conf. Intell. Transp. Syst.(ITSC), Oct. 2011, pp. 979–984.
- [2] Y. Geng and C. G. Cassandras, "New smart parking system based on resource allocation and reservations, IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst., vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 1129–1139, Sep. 2013.
- [3] X. Zhao, K. Zhao, and F. Hai, "An algorithm of parking planning for smart parking system, in Proc. 11th World Congr. Intell. Control Autom. (WCICA), 2014, pp. 4965–4969.
- [4] D. J. Bonde, R. S. Shende, K. S. Gaikwad, A. S. Kedari, and A. U. Bhokre, "Automated car parking system commanded by Android application," in Proc. Int. Conf. Comput. Commun. Inform. (ICCCI), 2014.
- [5] A Proposed Automated Car Parking System based on Android: Samiksha Nagmote¹, Pallavi Mane², Shubhangi Musle³, Shraddha Sarwade⁴(International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAEM) Volume 4, Issue 3, March 2015 ISSN
- [6] [6]Smart Parking System Based On Reservation: Mohit Patil,Rahul Sakure (International
- [7] Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (IJSER)), www.ijser.in , ISSN (Online):
- [8] 2347-3878, Volume 2 Issues 6, June 2014.
- [9] [7]Vehicle Parking System Using IoT: Dr. G.M.Rajathi, Mydilee.K.V.,T.Revathi (International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (IJSER)), www.ijser.in , ISSN (Online): 2229-5518, Volume 8 Issues 7, July 2017.
- [10] [8]Smart Parking System-A Survey: Mrs Bhavya G, Raksha N, Raksha Poornashri M,Rashmita Prabhakar (International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (IJSER)),
- [11] www.ijser.in , ISSN (Online): 2229-5518, Volume 7, Issues 5, May 2016.
- [12] [9] Zheng, Y., Rajasegarar, S., & Leckie, C. (2015, April). Parking availability prediction for sensor-enabled car parks in smart cities. In Intelligent Sensors, Sensor Networks and Information Processing (ISSNIP), 2015 IEEE Tenth International Conference on (pp. 1- 6).IEEE.
- [13] [10] Botta, A., de Donato, W., Persico, V., & Pescapé, A. (2014, August). On the Integration of Cloud Computing and Internet of Things. In Future Internet of Things and Cloud (FiCloud), 2014 International Conference on (pp. 23-30). IEEE.
- [14] [11] Ji, Z., Ganchev, I., O'droma, M., & Zhang, X. (2014, August). A cloudbased intelligent car parking services for smart cities. In General Assembly and Scientific Symposium (URSI GASS), 2014 XXXIth URSI (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [15] [12] Dash, S. K., Mohapatra, S., & Pattnaik, P. K. (2010). A survey on applications of wireless sensor network using cloud
- [16] computing. International Journal of Computer science & Engineering Technologies (E-ISSN: 2044-6004), 1(4), 50-55.
- [17] [13] Fox, G. C., Kamburugamuve, S., & Hartman, R. D. (2012, May). Architecture and measured characteristics of a cloud based internet of things. In Collaboration Technologies and Systems (CTS), 2012 International Conference on (pp. 6-12). IEEE.
- [18] [14] Han, D. M., & Lim, J. H. (2010). Smart home energy management system using IEEE 802.15. 4 and zigbee. Consumer Electronics, IEEE Transactions on, 56(3), 1403-1410.
- [19] [15] Parwekar, P. (2011, September). From Internet of Things towards cloud of things. In Computer and Communication Technology (ICCCT), 2011 2nd International Conference on (pp. 329-333). IEEE.
- [20] Wikipedia website, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_of_things
- [21] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Real-time-computing>
- [22] [17] Suci, G., Vulpe, A., Halunga, S., Fratu, O., Todoran, G., & Suci, V.(2013, May). Smart cities built on resilient cloud computing and secure internet of things. In Control Systems and Computer Science (CSCS), 2013 19th International Conference on (pp. 513-518). IEEE.

